

Effective Employment of the Narrative Technique, Stream of Consciousness in James Joyce's Short Story "Eveline"

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Abstract

James Joyce is a renowned Irish poet, novelist and literary critic. He is known for his ground-breaking contribution to the modern literature through his usage of experimental techniques such as Stream of Consciousness, Complex Symbolism and Non-linear narratives. His notable works include *Dubliners*, *A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man*, *Ulysses* and *Finnegans Wake*. James Joyce's works are known for their depth and ability to capture the essence of human thoughts and emotions. This study aims at the analysis of the short story "Eveline" so as to bring out his treatment of the stream of consciousness as a powerful narrative technique. According to M.H. Abrams, the Stream of Consciousness is a mode of narration that undertakes to reproduce the full spectrum and continuous flow of a character's mental process in which sense perceptions mingle with conscious and half-conscious thoughts, memories, expectations, feelings and random associations. James Joyce delves deep into the character Eveline's non-linear thought process and gives a reader an access to her inner conflict and reflection on her past and future. In the early 20th century, the employment opportunities for women were limited. The society expected them to do the household chores and the duty towards the family welfare. James Joyce delineates vividly the emotional and psychological struggles of a young woman Eveline. She is overwhelmed by her responsibilities, in the absence of her mother. She has to take care of her younger siblings and endure the abuse of her squandering father. Eveline's love towards Frank has made her think of her personal freedom but the promise which she has given to her mother stops her from going away from the family by joining hands with Frank. Eveline undergoes a dilemma and it is revealed effectively by the usage of stream of consciousness technique. Despite the longing for a new and peaceful life, she is unable to overcome her past and face her future. She is trapped in the present life of hardship. James Joyce has brought out the thought process of the mind of Eveline which flows naturally and it moves forward the action of the story.

Key words: Stream of Consciousness, Narrative Technique, Non-linear, Memory, Society, and Thought Process.

James Augustine Aloysius Joyce is an Irish poet, novelist and literary critic. He was born in Dublin, Ireland. He is one of the important writers of the 20th century. He is the pioneer of Modern Literature and he has contributed to the modernist avant-garde movement. It reflects the cultural and societal changes that occurred at that time. It is characterized by inventive techniques like fragmented or non-linear narrative and stream of consciousness narrative that mirror the thoughts and memories flowing in the character's mind. Writers like James Joyce, Virginia Woolf, Dorothy Richardson, and William Faulkner have captured the subjective realities and individual consciousness in their writings. Instead of external actions, they have delved into the minds of the characters by presenting fragmented and

often non-linear thought patterns to reflect the complexities of human experience. His notable works include *Dubliners*, a collection of short stories, and the novels *A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man*, *Ulysses* and *Finnegans Wake*. He has used the stream of consciousness technique very effectively in his works. It delineates the spontaneous thought process, shifting of memories and emotions. James Joyce has showcased this narrative style to prioritize internal experiences over external occurrences. This study aims at an analysis of the short story "Eveline" so as to bring out his treatment of the stream of consciousness as a powerful narrative technique.

According to M.H. Abrams, the Stream of Consciousness is a mode of narration that undertakes to reproduce the full spectrum and continuous flow of a character's mental process in which sense perceptions mingle with conscious and half-conscious thoughts, memories, expectations, feelings and random associations. Virginia Woolf in her novels, *Mrs. Dalloway* and *To the Lighthouse* uses the narrative technique stream of consciousness to explore the characters' thoughts, and memories, and captures the interconnectedness of their past and present lives. James Joyce in his short story collection, *Dubliners* paints a vivid picture of life in Dublin. He depicts movingly the day-to-day life struggles of ordinary people. James Joyce's writing style is known for its detailed realism and interior monologue, and it makes readers feel like that they are walking in the street of Dublin.

James Joyce has employed a third person limited point of view as the mode of narration in the short story "Eveline." It allows the reader delve into the thoughts of Eveline and captures her internal feelings through the usage of the narrative technique stream of consciousness. James Joyce delineates vividly the emotional and psychological struggles of a young woman Eveline. She is overwhelmed by her responsibilities, in the absence of her mother. She has to take care of her younger siblings and endure the abuse of her squandering father. Eveline's love towards Frank has made her think of her personal freedom but the promise which she has given to her mother stops her from going away from the family commitments by joining hands with Frank. Joyce's usage of language that mimics her flow of thoughts instead of mere description of her feelings. Her thoughts flow in a non-linear structure and it jumps into past memories to present life and vice-versa.

The story begins with the Eveline's inner flow of thoughts when she recalls her childhood memories, "The children of the avenue used to play together in that field" (34). Her father who was not bad then and she was happy with her mother who was alive at that time. She reviews the familiar things in her home and she wants to get rid of her home desperately: "Still they seemed to have been rather happy then. Her father was not so bad then; and besides, her mother was alive. That was a long time ago; she and her brothers and sisters were all grown up; her mother was dead. Tizzie Dunn was dead, too, and the Waters had gone back to England. Everything changes. Now she was going to go away like the others, to leave her home" (34).

She lives with the empty heart and decides to go away. She questions herself whether it is a wise decision. She has the shelter and food, and she has to go for work. She has to work hard in both outside and inside for family. At times, her father is so rude in the absence of her mother and she thinks of escape from his torture. Sometimes, he remains good. She experiences the dilemma of leaving the house or not. She thinks of the opinions of people. They may ask about her runaway. She questions herself:

She had consented to go away, to leave her home. Was that wise? She tried to weigh each side of the question. In her home anyway she had shelter and food; she had those whom she had known all her life about her. Of course she had to work hard, both in the house and at business. What would they say of her in the stores when they found out that she had run away with a fellow? Say she was fool, perhaps; and her place would be filled up by advertisement (35).

James Joyce has employed the stream of consciousness effectively in the passage when she has revealed the thought process of Eveline's mind. She experiences the difficulty to take a decision and she struggles to arrive at any action. She thinks of her family members and she is worried about the opinions of people at her place of work and other neighbours. It reveals the artistic employment of the narrative technique of James Joyce and the readers experience the dilemma of the character at first hand.

Her father's indifference also is presented by the writer effectively when Eveline thinks of him: "Even now, though she was over nineteen, she sometimes felt herself in danger of her father's violence. She knew it was that that had given her the palpitations" (35). In fact, she feels the insecurity and her father also has turned against her at times. At the same time, she remembers the promise she has made to her mother that to take care of the family. James Joyce adeptly presents the thought process of Eveline's mind and makes the readers to get a good fictional experience at first hand.

Eveline remembers the first meeting with Frank who is very kind, manly and open-hearted person as observed by her. They get to know each other and meet every evening. She feels elated, when he has taken her to see *The Bohemian Girl* in an unaccustomed part of the theatre. She is excited by his company and good manners. He is a sailor and he is fond of music. She wants to explore another life with him as his wife, later she thinks that her father is getting old and he must need her presence. The non-linear thought process occurs in this segment. Even though she is in the danger of her father's violence, she feels pity for him by remembering their childhood days when her father has done many things to make them laugh. Eveline always remembers her promise to her mother of taking care of their family. Her flow of thoughts continues and she sits and inhales the odour of dusty cretonne: "Down far in the avenue she could hear a street organ playing. She knew the air. Strange that it should come that very night to remind her of the promise to her mother, her promise to keep the home together as long as she could" (38). She remembers her promise to her mother and it lingers her mind. In the last night of her ill-mother, the organ-player plays the melancholic song of Italy. She understands the life of her mother who has sacrificed many things for her family. James Joyce writes: "She trembled as she heard again her mother's voice saying constantly with foolish insistence: *Derevaun Seraun! Derevaun Seraun!*" (39). The Phrase "*Derevaun Seraun*" refers to "the end of pain is pleasure" or "the end of freedom."

The last words of her mother urge her to go with Frank and get freedom from the demanding and taxing life in her home. She wants to escape from the household chores and responsibilities. Eveline convinces herself that she has the right to live happily with Frank. She thinks: "Escape! She must escape! Frank would save her. He would give her life, perhaps love, too. But she wanted to live. Why should she be unhappy? She had a right to happiness. Frank would take her in his arms, fold her in his arms. He would save her" (39). James Joyce has succeeded in showing the inner conflict of the character Eveline vividly by using the stream of consciousness technique. He presents the predicament of Eveline in an effective manner. Now, she decides to move with Frank. Frank and Eveline are about to board into the ship. At that time, she remains silent and feels her cheek pale and cold. She is entangled in misery and she prays to God to direct her. She wants to know her real duty and freedom. If she goes with Frank, she will lead a happy life with him in Buenos Ayres. When the whistle blew for the boarding of boat, suddenly she stalls her decision and stands still with an unknown fear occurred into heart. She still keeps moving her lips in silent prayer:

A bell clanged upon her heart. She felt him seize her hand:

'Come!'

All the seas of the world tumbled about her heart. He was drawing her into them: he would drown her. She gripped with both hands at the iron railing.

'Come!'

No! No! No! It was impossible. Her hands clutched the iron in frenzy. Amid the sea she sent a cry of anguish.

'Eveline! Evvy!'

He rushed beyond the barrier and called to her to follow. He was shouted at to go on, but he still called to her. She set her white face to him, passive, like a helpless animal. Her eyes gave him no sign of love or farewell or recognition. (40)

Eveline is completely paralyzed both at physical and emotional level. She taken the decision of taking care of the family including the aged father and siblings rather than settling herself in a new life with her partner Frank. This decision of Eveline reveals her boldness in facing the hardships of life and

shouldering the responsibility of household. Further, her sacrifice of leading a happy life with partner Frank for the sake of her family. James Joyce has effectively portrayed the internal struggle of Eveline and adeptly used the stream of consciousness technique to reveal it.

Eveline struggles to overcome her past especially the promise she has made for her mother that of taking care of their family. She faces the difficulty to take a decision for her future. She suffers in her present life with hardship due to this. James Joyce has presented skilfully the duality between her longing for freedom and her sense of duty to her family through the employment of stream of consciousness technique. He portrays the inner conflict of Eveline and the flow of non-linear thoughts by using aptly the narrative technique stream of consciousness. He allows the reader to access and connects with her emotional conflicts. The reader becomes a witness to see her internal struggle and the writer adeptly presents her tension and indecision through the narrative technique stream of consciousness.

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